

Development and validation of UV-spectroscopy based stability indicating different methods for the determination of Canagliflozin

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Abstract: Simple and sensitive spectroscopic methods in UV region and visible region were developed for the estimation of Canagliflozin in its pharmaceutical dosage forms. The development and validation of these methods as a stability indicating assay based on the forced degradation studies. Method A was based on Canagliflozin showing its absorption maxima at 290 nm in ethanol. The method B was based on Canagliflozin showing its absorption maxima at 280 nm in methanol. The method C was colorimetric. It involved the reaction of Canagliflozin with ceric ammonium sulphate in presence of H₂SO₄ and crystal violet that produced a blue colour, showed absorption maxima at 578 nm. These methods obey Beer-Lambert law at concentration ranges of 5–25 µg/mL, 8–12 µg/mL and 5–25 µg/mL respectively. The percent recoveries were found out to be 98–102%. The results obtained with the proposed methods were in good agreement with the labeled amount when tablet dosage forms were analyzed.

Keywords: Canagliflozin, UV spectroscopy, method development, colorimetric method.

Introduction

Type-2 diabetes mellitus is a progressive disease resulting from an insulin secretory defect characterized by insulin resistance and some degree of insulin deficiency. The prevalence of the disease is increased in obese patients, minority populations, and the elderly. Chronic long-term hyperglycemia associated with diabetes is the cause of serious complications, including blindness, kidney failure, amputations, and death. In March 2013, the FDA approved Canagliflozin as an adjunct to diet and exercise for adults with type-2 diabetes mellitus. This is the first oral agent in a novel class of diabetes drugs known as sodium-glucose co-transporter-2 (SGLT-2) inhibitors¹.

Canagliflozin ((2*S*,3*R*,4*R*,5*S*,6*R*)-2-{3-[5-[4-fluoro-phenyl]-thiophen-2-ylmethyl]-4-methyl-phenyl}-6-hydroxymethyl-tetrahydro-pyran-3,4,5-triol)² (Fig. 1).

Canagliflozin hemihydrate drug substance is a

Fig. 1. Structure of Canagliflozin.

white to off white powder, soluble in many organic solvents (ethanol, methanol, tetrahydrofuran, and acetone) but insoluble in aqueous media. The log *P* of the drug substance is 3.44 at 20°C and pH 7. There is no p*K*_a in the physiological pH range. Canagliflozin is an orally active inhibitor of SGLT-2. By inhibiting SGLT-2, Canagliflozin reduces re-absorption of filtered glucose and lowers the renal threshold for glucose and thereby increases urinary glucose excretion, lowering elevated plasma glucose concentrations by an insulin independent mechanism in patients with type-2 diabetes³.

As per the literature survey, it is revealed that the drug has been estimated by liquid chromatography^{4,5}

and ultra-high performance liquid chromatography-Mass spectroscopy (UHPLC-MS)⁶ in biological fluids⁷ like rat and plasma. Some UV-spectroscopic method and liquid chromatography analysis has been reported for the estimation in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form⁸⁻¹¹. There is no paper for colorimetric method for Canagliflozin.

The aim and objective of the present work is to develop and validate two spectrophotometric and one colorimetric method for determination of Canagliflozin in its tablet dosage form. The methods was validated in compliance with ICH guidelines^{9,10}.

Results and discussion

The proposed methods provide a simple, accurate, economical, and convenient way for the analysis of Canagliflozin by UV-Visible Spectroscopy. In method C Canagliflozin was estimated based on the reaction between ceric ammonium sulphate and crystal violet in the presence of acidic medium. When ceric ammonium sulphate was added in excess amount, it produces a complex of Canagliflozin. Unreacted ceric ammonium sulphate readily reacts with crystal violet

and oxidized crystal violet. Unreacted molecules of crystal violet gave blue colour. So, colour of the final solution indirectly indicates the amount of drug present (Fig. 2).

The absorbance spectra of Canagliflozin in method A, method B and method C is 290 nm, 280 nm and 578 nm respectively (Fig. 3). In the developed method, linearity was observed and calibration plot were shown in Fig. 4 for all methods. The accuracy of the proposed methods checked by standard addition method and was found within the specified range thus indicated the accuracy of the methods (Table 2). The precision of the methods were found for 10 µg/mL samples within the limit (<2% RSD) proves the precision of methods (Table 3).

The ruggedness of the methods were determined by performing the same method by using different analysts at similar operational and environmental condition. The result was reported in Table 4. The robustness of the proposed method was established by percent recovery and percent RSD of the sample on the same day. The result proves the robustness of the methods (Table 5). The limit of detection of the

Fig. 2. Oxidation reaction for the development of colour.

Fig. 3. Absorption spectra of Canagliflozin complex.

method A, method B and method C were found to be 0.11 µg/mL, 0.079 µg/mL, 0.48 µg/mL respectively.

The limit of quantitation of the method A, method B and method C were found to be 0.344 µg/mL, 0.238 µg/mL, 1.47 µg/mL respectively. Force degradation studies of Canagliflozin were shown in Table 6. The summary of optical characteristics and validation parameters of method A, method B and method C were shown in Table 7.

Fig. 4. Linearity curve of Canagliflozin.

Table 1. Selection of wavelength, preparation of stock and working standard solution in all methods

Methods	Wavelength (nm)	Concentration of stock (µg/mL)	Concentration of working standard (µg/mL)
Method A	290	100	50
Method B	280	100	20
Method C	578	100	50

Experimental

Instrumentation:

An UV/Vis double beam spectrophotometer (UV-1800, Shimadzu), having 1 cm matched quartz cell, loaded with UV probe software was used for recording and measuring of spectra and absorbance. All weighing was performed over 0.1 mg sensitivity citizen CX 220 and a sonicator (Hicon, model 1.5L (H)) were used in the study.

The working standard of Canagliflozin was pro-

Table 2A. Precision result (system)

Method A		Method B		Method C	
Concentration (µg/mL)	Absorbance	Concentration (µg/mL)	Absorbance	Concentration (µg/mL)	Absorbance
10	0.466	10	0.406	10	0.048
10	0.463	10	0.410	10	0.047
10	0.464	10	0.408	10	0.046
10	0.468	10	0.406	10	0.047
10	0.463	10	0.409	10	0.048
10	0.460	10	0.406	10	0.047
Mean	0.464	Mean	0.407	Mean	0.047
SD	0.00275	SD	0.00176	SD	0.00075
%RSD	0.591	%RSD	0.432	%RSD	1.59

Table 2B. Precision result (method)

Concentration (10 µg/ml)	Intra-day study			Inter-day study		
	Morning	Afternoon	Evening	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3
Method A:						
Avg. abs.	0.481	0.464	0.446	0.483	0.445	0.444
SD	0.001527	0.001537	0.001154	0.002	0.00230	0.00208
%RSD	0.317	0.317	0.258	0.414	0.516	0.468
Method B:						
Avg. abs.	0.397	0.408	0.443	0.398	0.406	0.429
SD	0.00251	0.002	0.001527	0.00057	0.00305	0.001
%RSD	0.632	0.490	0.344	0.143	0.752	0.233
Method C:						
Avg. abs.	0.044	0.048	0.050	0.049	0.051	0.042
SD	0.00057	0.0005	0.0005	0.00073	0.0002	0.00073
%RSD	1.29	1.18	1.14	1.48	0.392	1.73

Table 3. Accuracy result

Level	Abs.			%Recovery			Mean % recovery		
	Method			Method			Method		
	A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C
80	0.366	0.320	0.037	98.38	98.76	98.36	98.74	99.48	98.81
80	0.367	0.325	0.036	98.65	100.3	98.08			
80	0.369	0.322	0.038	99.19	99.38	100.0			
100	0.468	0.410	0.049	100.4	100.9	102.0	100.4	100.6	101.3
100	0.469	0.409	0.048	100.6	100.2	100.0			
100	0.467	0.407	0.049	100.2	100.2	102.0			
120	0.568	0.495	0.058	101.61	101.6	101.7	101.7	102.2	101.8
120	0.565	0.501	0.058	101.07	102.8	101.7			
120	0.562	0.499	0.059	100.53	102.4	102.0			

cured from CHEMSCENE, NJ USA. The marketed formulation Sulisent (100 mg) tablets were procured from USV Limited in India. Methanol and ethanol

was from Merk Specialties Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai. All chemicals were at least of analytical grade and used as received. Purified water was obtained by reverse

Table 4. Ruggedness result

Analyst	Abs.			SD			%RSD		
	Method			Method			Method		
	A	B	C	A	B	C	A	B	C
Analyst 1	0.445	0.404	0.043	0.0020	0.0026	0.0005	0.44	0.64	1.16
	0.442	0.408	0.044				0.45	0.63	1.13
	0.441	0.403	0.043				0.45	0.64	1.16
Analyst 2	0.440	0.410	0.041	0.0030	0.0058	0.0005	0.68	1.48	1.21
	0.442	0.408	0.040				0.67	1.48	1.25
	0.446	0.399	0.041				0.67	1.45	1.21

osmosis and filtration through a milli-Q® system (Millipore, Milford, MA, USA) and was used to prepare all solutions.

Materials and reagents:

Canagliflozin is freely soluble in methanol, ethanol and dimethyl sulfoxide so ethanol and methanol were selected throughout the study. Selection of wavelength, preparation of stock solution and standard solution for all methods were shown in Table 1.

Table 5. Robustness result

Wavelength (nm)	Sample Abs.	Standard Abs.	SD	%RSD
Method A: 289	0.413	0.465	0.00057	0.12
	0.412			
	0.413			
291	0.414	0.467	0.00152	0.365
	0.415			
	0.417			
Method B: 289	0.420	0.404	0.0028	0.69
	0.420			
	0.425			
291	0.422	0.414	0.001	0.24
	0.421			
	0.423			
Method C: 577	0.039	0.048	0.0005	1.04
	0.040			
	0.040			
579	0.047	0.042	0.0001	0.23
	0.045			
	0.045			

Preparation of reagents for method C:

Preparation of 0.5% w/v ceric ammonium sulphate: Weigh accurately 500 mg of ceric ammonium sulphate (pure) in a 100 mL volumetric flask, to this add approximately 1 mL of concentrated sulphuric acid dropwise to dissolve the powder and make up the remaining volume upto the mark with distilled water¹⁵.

Preparation of 4 M H₂SO₄: 11.1 mL of concentrated H₂SO₄ was taken in a measuring cylinder and was carefully transferred into a 100 mL volumetric flask that already had 20 mL distilled water, water was added to the flask to make up the volume¹⁵.

Preparation of 0.015% w/v of crystal violet: 100 mg of crystal violet (pure form) was weighed accurately and transferred to a 100 mL volumetric flask and sufficient distilled water was added to dissolve initially. Later the volume was made upto the mark with distilled water and 15 mL from the above solution was pipette and transferred to a 100 mL volumetric flask and the volume was made up to 100 mL with distilled water¹⁵.

Preparation of calibration curve:

Method A:

From this stock solution appropriate dilution were made to get final concentration of 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 µg/mL and absorbance was taken at λ_{\max} 290 nm. Averages of such 5 sets of values were taken for standard calibration curve, and the calibration curve was plotted.

Method B:

From this stock solution appropriate dilution were made to get final concentration of 8, 9, 10, 11, 12

Table 6. Force degradation studies

Test preparation	% Drug remained			% Drug degraded		
	Method			Method		
	A	B	C	A	B	C
Control sample	100.0	100.0	100.0	0	0	0
Base stress (4 h)	98.09	99.14	98.07	1.91	0.86	1.93
Base stress (8 h)	96.03	97.40	96.12	3.97	2.60	3.88
Base stress (24 h)	93.08	95.62	92.14	6.92	4.38	7.86
Acid stress (4 h)	95.48	97.92	97.04	4.52	2.08	2.96
Acid stress (8 h)	91.18	95.42	90.01	8.82	4.58	9.99
6% Peroxide treated (4 h)	98.05	99.10	99.01	1.95	0.90	0.99
6% Peroxide treated (8 h)	95.76	96.24	95.67	4.24	3.76	4.33
Heat (24 h)	99.49	100.0	90.43	0.51	0	9.57
Heat (48 h)	97.24	99.01	80.07	2.76	0.99	19.93
Light (5 days)	100.0	99.40	88.01	0	0.60	11.99
Light (10 days)	98.61	98.60	80.09	1.39	1.40	19.91

Table 7. Summary of optical characteristics and validation parameters

Parameters	Method A	Method B	Method C
	Result	Result	Result
Detection wavelength (nm)	290	280	578
Beer's law limits ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	5–25	8–12	5–25
Regression equation	$Y = 0.0581x - 0.1956$	$Y = 0.0413x - 0.0539$	$Y = 0.0051x - 0.0035$
Correlation coefficient	0.9994	0.999	0.9995
Slope (m)	0.0581	0.0413	0.0051
Intercept (c)	0.1956	0.0539	0.0035
Precision (%RSD)			
Intra-day	0.25–0.31	0.34–0.63	1.1–1.2
Inter-day	0.41–0.51	0.14–0.75	0.3–1.7
Accuracy (%mean recovery)			
80% level	98.74	99.48	98.81
100% level	100.4	100.6	101.3
120% level	101.7	101.2	101.8
Ruggedness			
2 Analyst (%RSD)	<2	<2	<2
Robustness			
Wavelength (+2 nm, -2 nm) %RSD	<2	<2	<2

$\mu\text{g/mL}$ and absorbance was taken at λ_{max} 280 nm. Averages of such 5 sets of values were taken for standard calibration curve, and the calibration curve was plotted.

Method C:

From this stock solution 1 to 5 mL were transferred into a series of 10 ml volumetric flasks. To each flask 0.5 mL of 0.5% CAS was added, fol-

lowed by 1 mL of 4 M H_2SO_4 and was kept aside for 20 min. Then 1.5 mL of crystal violet solution was added and the volume was made up to mark with methanol. Appropriate dilution were made to get final concentration of 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and absorbance was taken at λ_{max} 578 nm. Averages of such 5 sets of values were taken for standard calibration curve, and the calibration curve was plotted.

Method validation:

The development and validation of analytical procedure with respect to linearity, precision, accuracy, robustness, and ruggedness, limit of detection and limit of quantitation were developed according to ICH guidelines¹²⁻¹⁴.

Linearity:

The linearity was established across the range and the absorbance of standard stock solution in different media in the range of 5–25 µg/mL in method A, 8–12 µg/mL in method B and 5–25 µg/mL in method C. The calibration curves were prepared by plotting graph between average absorbance ($n = 3$) and concentration. Linearity was determined by least square regression method.

Precision:

System precision: Six replicates recording of absorbance at 290 nm of 10 µg/mL concentration standard solution showed %RSD (Relative Standard Deviation) less than 2 in method A, which indicates acceptable reproducibility and thereby the precision of the system. Six replicates recording of absorbance at 280 nm of 10 µg/mL concentration standard solution showed %RSD (Relative Standard Deviation) less than 2 in method B, which indicates acceptable reproducibility and thereby the precision of the system.

Six replicates recording of absorbance at 578 nm of 10 µg/mL concentration standard solution showed %RSD (Relative Standard Deviation) less than 2 in method C, which indicates acceptable reproducibility and thereby the precision of the system.

Method precision:

It was determined by performing assay of sample under the test of (i) Intra-day precision and (ii) Inter-day precision. In the intra-day study three different solution of the same concentration (10 µg/mL) were prepared and analysed thrice a day (morning, afternoon, evening) in method A, B, C. In the intra-day variation study, the solution of same concentration (10 µg/mL) were prepared and analysed daily for three days, and the absorbance was recorded in method A, B, C.

Accuracy:

Accuracy was determined by performing recovery experiments in which determination of % mean recovery of sample by percentage method at three different levels (80–120%). 80–120% of the solution were prepared as per the procedure given in the methods from the dilutions used for the linearity (10 µg/mL) in method A, B, C. At each level, three different analyses were performed. Percent mean recovery was calculated. The accepted limits of recovery are 98–102% and all observed data were within the required range which indicates good recovery values and hence the accuracy of the method developed.

Ruggedness:

Ruggedness was determined by performing the same proposed method on different instrument. Also, method was carried out by two different analysts and by performing the method on different days to check the reproducibility. In these three methods %RSD were less than 2 and that indicated the developed method is rugged.

Robustness:

Robustness is the ability of a method to remain unaffected by small deliberate variation in method parameters. It is determined by performing the analysis at slightly different wavelength from the selected wavelength. In these three methods %RSD were less than 2.

Detection limit and quantitation limit:

The detection limit and the quantitation limit were based on the slope of the calibration curve and the standard deviation of Y-intercept of regression line.

Forced degradation studies:

Canagliflozin was allowed to hydrolyze in the base (0.1 N NaOH), acid (0.1 N HCl) and hydrogen peroxide (10% v/v). Canagliflozin was also studied for its thermal degradation at 80°C for 2 days and photolytic degradation for 10 days, exposed to white fluorescent light (1.2 million lux) near UV fluorescent light (200 w/m²). Powdered tablet equivalent to 5 mg drug was accurately weighed and transferred to 50 ml clean volumetric flask and volume were

made up with 0.1 N NaOH solution, 0.1 N HCl and hydrogen peroxide 10% v/v kept at room temperature to accelerate the degradation. 1 mL of sample was taken out at various time intervals, and it was neutralized with 0.1 N HCl solution and 0.1 N NaOH diluted with solvent to get the final concentration of 10 µg/mL of Canagliflozin. Similarly, placebo solution was prepared. Sample and placebo solutions were analyzed as per methodology, calculated the percentage degradation.

Conclusion

The most critical parameter is stability of any drug which may affect purity, potency and safety. It is very essential to know the purity profile and behavior of drug substance under various environmental conditions. The reproducibility, repeatability, and accuracy of these methods were found to be good, which is evident by low standard deviation values. The percent recovery experiment values obtained indicates non-interference from the excipients used in the formulations. The percentage recovery was close to 100% for these methods. Thus, it can be concluded that the method developed was simple, accurate, sensitive and precise. Hence, these can be successfully applied in the estimation of Canagliflozin. The proposed method can be used for routine quality control analysis of Canagliflozin in its pharmaceutical formulation. The most striking feature of these methods is its simplicity and low cost.

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